

Snap-through and Eulerian buckling of the bi-stable von Mises truss in nonlinear elasticity: A theoretical, numerical and experimental investigation

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Abstract

In this paper, the equilibrium and stability of the von Mises truss subjected to a vertical load is analyzed from theoretical, numerical and experimental points of view. The bars of the truss are composed of a rubber material, so that large deformations can be observed. The analytical model of the truss is developed in the fully nonlinear context of finite elasticity and the constitutive behavior of the rubber is modeled using a Mooney-Rivlin law. The constitutive parameters are identified by means of a genetic algorithm that fits experimental data from uniaxial tests on rubber specimens. The numerical analysis is performed through a finite element (FE) model. Differently from the analytical and FE simulations that can be found in the literature, the models presented in this work are entirely developed in three-dimensional finite elasticity. Experiments are conducted with a device that allows the rubber specimens to undergo large axial deformations. For the first time, snap-through is observed experimentally on rubber materials, showing good agreement with both theoretical and numerical results. Further insights on Eulerian buckling of the rubber specimens and its interaction with the snap-through are given. A simple formulation to determine the critical load of the truss is presented and its accuracy is validated through experimental observation. Comparisons with a linear elasticity based approach demonstrate that an accurate prediction of snap-through and Eulerian buckling requires nonlinear formulations, such as the ones proposed in this work.

Keywords: Nonlinear elasticity; Snap-through; Truss; Eulerian buckling; Experimental mechanics

1. Introduction

The equilibrium of the von Mises truss (Mises, 1923) subjected to a vertical load is a benchmark problem in the analysis of the stability of truss structures because it exhibits various post-critical behaviors, such as snap-through and bifurcation (Bellini, 1972; Pecknold et al., 1985; Savi et al., 2002). The von Mises truss is a bistable system and thus it is used to obtain structures with multiple stable configurations (Schioler & Pellegrino, 2007; Danso & Karpov, 2017; Orlando et al., 2018; Schorr et al., 2018). Applications can be found in different fields of engineering, such as lattice truss structures (López et al., 2007; Pellicciari & Tarantino, 2020b) and metamaterials (Paulose et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2021). Structural morphing applications are also of great interest (Barbarino et al., 2013). For instance, Moser et al. (2014) used a centrifugally actuated von Mises truss for the morphing mechanism of helicopter rotor blades.

Analytical solutions for the equilibrium of the von Mises truss are important tests for the validation of numerical procedures. A solution under the assumptions of linear elastic (LE) material and moderate axial deformations was proposed by Kwasniewski (2009). Afterwards, these assumptions were abandoned by Pellicciari & Tarantino (2020a) and a solution including both geometric and material nonlinearities was

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Figure 1: The von Mises truss: (a) Kinematics; (b) Three-dimensional bodies and corresponding fixed and principal reference systems.

presented. The kinematics of the system was based on the hypothesis of homogeneous deformations, therefore Eulerian buckling was neglected.

In this work, the von Mises truss subjected to a vertical load is analyzed from analytic, numerical and experimental points of view. The bars of the truss are composed of a rubber material so that large deformations can be observed. The materials classically employed in constructions, such as concrete and steel, hardly experience large deformations when subjected to compression. This is the reason why in the literature there is lack of experimental tests involving both large displacements and deformations.

The experimental tests of the present work are performed with a device specifically designed to avoid Eulerian buckling of the bars. This condition reproduces a behavior as close as possible to that of truss structures. Theoretical, numerical and experimental equilibrium paths are compared in order to demonstrate the soundness of the methods proposed. Furthermore, an analytical approach to account for Eulerian buckling of the bars in nonlinear elasticity is presented. Additional experimental tests are carried out and Eulerian buckling is experimentally observed, providing a validation of the analytical approach proposed.

The analytical solution is based on the formulation proposed by Pellicciari & Tarantino (2020a) and it is presented in Section 2, assuming a Mooney-Rivlin (MR) constitutive law. The case of LE constitutive law, which corresponds to the theory proposed by Kwasniewski (2009), is also outlined. The uniaxial tests for rubber characterization and the experimental investigation of the von Mises truss are described in Section 3. Section 4 contains a description of the FE models for the numerical analysis, while Section 5 presents the strategy for fitting the constitutive model to experimental data. Analytical, numerical and experimental results are presented and discussed in Section 6. The results of the analytical models with MR and LE materials are compared and the effect of Eulerian buckling on the behavior of the truss is investigated with additional experiments. Concluding remarks are given in Section 7.

2. Analytical formulation

2.1. Kinematics and equilibrium

The von Mises truss of Figure 1 consists of two equal straight bars connected through a hinge at node C . The bars are composed of an inner deformable material, while the terminal parts are rigid elements. The length of the terminal parts is L_r and it represents the space occupied by the hinge in the experimental device, which is presented in Section 3.2. The length of the inner deformable part is L_m .

As shown in Figure 1a, the apex node C is loaded by the external dead load force F , acting in the Z direction of the global reference system C_1XYZ . Under the effect of the external load, node C undergoes the vertical displacement \hat{w} . Note that the horizontal degree of freedom of control point C is not considered in this work. This because the results presented in (Pellicciari & Tarantino, 2020a) demonstrated that stable solutions can be found only along the vertical degree of freedom.

The entire length of both bars in reference configuration is $L = \sqrt{B^2 + H^2}$, while in deformed configuration $l = \sqrt{B^2 + (H - \hat{w})^2}$. The length of the deformable part of the bars in reference configuration is

$$L_m = \sqrt{(B - 2L_r \cos \theta_0)^2 + (H - 2L_r \sin \theta_0)^2}, \quad (1)$$

whereas in deformed configuration

$$l_m = \sqrt{(B - 2L_r \cos \theta)^2 + (H - \hat{w} - 2L_r \sin \theta)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$\cos \theta_0 = \frac{B}{L}, \quad \cos \theta = \frac{B}{l}, \quad \sin \theta_0 = \frac{H}{L}, \quad \sin \theta = \frac{H - \hat{w}}{l}, \quad (3)$$

being θ_0 and θ the inclination angle of the truss in reference and deformed configurations, respectively.

The bars are three-dimensional bodies with a rectangular cross section of width t and height h , as shown in Figure 1b. It is assumed that the material is homogeneous, isotropic and hyperelastic. The deformation of the bodies is assumed to be homogeneous.

The fixed material coordinate systems $C_i X_i Y_i Z_i$ ($i = 1, 2$) are defined. In addition, the coordinate systems $C_i x_i y_i z_i$ are established in deformed configuration. As depicted in Figure 1b, the reference systems $C_i x_i y_i z_i$ follow the rigid rotation ψ of the bodies, thus they are principal. This makes them convenient for the definition of the principal stretches λ_j ($j = x, y, z$), which represent the pure deformation. Figure 1b shows that the bodies rotate around axes Y_1 and Y_2 . Therefore, axes y_1 and y_2 of the principal reference systems correspond to axes Y_1 and Y_2 , respectively.

Under the above assumptions, the stored energy function $W(\iota_1, \iota_2, \iota_3)$ depends only on the principal invariants of the Cauchy-Green deformation tensor, defined as

$$\iota_1 = \lambda_x^2 + \lambda_y^2 + \lambda_z^2, \quad \iota_2 = \lambda_x^2 \lambda_y^2 + \lambda_x^2 \lambda_z^2 + \lambda_y^2 \lambda_z^2, \quad \iota_3 = \lambda_x^2 \lambda_y^2 \lambda_z^2. \quad (4)$$

Due to symmetry, the two bars undergo the same deformation field. The expression of the longitudinal stretch of the bars is

$$\lambda_z = \frac{l_m}{L_m} = \frac{\sqrt{(B - 2L_r \cos \theta)^2 + (H - \hat{w} - 2L_r \sin \theta)^2}}{\sqrt{(B - 2L_r \cos \theta_0)^2 + (H - 2L_r \sin \theta_0)^2}}. \quad (5)$$

The equilibrium in deformed configuration is expressed by

$$F + 2N \sin \theta = 0, \quad (6)$$

where N is the axial stress resultant of the bars.

The body forces are disregarded and the surface tractions generated by the concentrated load F are uniformly and orthogonally distributed on the basis of the bodies. Under the aforementioned assumptions, the solution of the boundary value problem leads to the following relations (Lanzoni & Tarantino, 2015; Pellicciari & Tarantino, 2020a):

$$\lambda_x = \lambda_y = \lambda = \sqrt{-\frac{W_{,1} + \lambda_z^2 W_{,2}}{W_{,2} + \lambda_z^2 W_{,3}}}, \quad (7)$$

$$N = -2th\lambda_z (W_{,2}^2 - W_{,1}W_{,3}) \frac{W_{,1} + 2\lambda_z^2 W_{,2} + \lambda_z^4 W_{,3}}{(W_{,2} + \lambda_z^2 W_{,3})^2}, \quad (8)$$

where $W_{,j} = \partial W / \partial \iota_j$ ($j = 1, 2, 3$). By introducing Eqs. (3), (7) and (8) into Eq. (6), the global equilibrium

equation of the von Mises truss becomes

$$F - 4th\lambda_z \frac{H - \hat{w}}{\sqrt{B^2 + (H - \hat{w})^2}} (W_{,2}^2 - W_{,1}W_{,3}) \frac{W_{,1} + 2\lambda_z^2 W_{,2} + \lambda_z^4 W_{,3}}{(W_{,2} + \lambda_z^2 W_{,3})^2} = 0. \quad (9)$$

Eq. (9) provides a direct relation between external load F and vertical displacement of the apex node \hat{w} , namely the equilibrium path.

The equilibrium equation can be alternatively obtained by introducing the total potential energy

$$\Pi(\hat{w}) = 2thL_m W - F\hat{w} \quad (10)$$

and its first derivative

$$\frac{d\Pi}{d\hat{w}} = 2thL_m \sum_{j=1}^3 \sum_k W_{,j} \frac{\partial \iota_j}{\partial \lambda_k} \frac{\partial \lambda_k}{\partial \hat{w}} - F, \quad k = x, y, z. \quad (11)$$

It is straightforward to verify that the stationarity condition $d\Pi/d\hat{w} = 0$ corresponds to the equilibrium equation (9).

2.2. Stability of the equilibrium

The stability of the equilibrium solutions is assessed through the energy criterion (Bažant & Cedolin, 1991; Ziegler, 2013). The second derivative of the total potential energy reads

$$\frac{d^2\Pi}{d\hat{w}^2} = thL_m \left[\sum_{j=1}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 W_{,kj} \left(\sum_p \frac{\partial \iota_k}{\partial \lambda_p} \frac{\partial \lambda_p}{\partial \hat{w}} \right) \left(\sum_q \frac{\partial \iota_j}{\partial \lambda_q} \frac{\partial \lambda_q}{\partial \hat{w}} \right) + \sum_{r=1}^3 W_{,r} \left(\sum_s \sum_t \frac{\partial^2 \iota_r}{\partial \lambda_t \partial \lambda_s} \frac{\partial \lambda_t}{\partial \hat{w}} \frac{\partial \lambda_s}{\partial \hat{w}} + \sum_s \frac{\partial \iota_r}{\partial \lambda_s} \frac{\partial^2 \lambda_s}{\partial \hat{w}^2} \right) \right], \quad (12)$$

with $l, p, r, s = x, y, z$. An equilibrium configuration is stable if the sign of the second derivative of $\Pi(\hat{w})$ is positive.

Since Eulerian buckling is neglected, the unstable phenomenon that takes place in the von Mises truss of Figure 1 is the snap-through. Specifically, when the external load reaches its maximum value, the system snaps to a non-adjacent equilibrium configuration.

Figure 2 defines five characteristic configurations: (0) reference configuration, where no external load is applied; (I) first critical point, where the load reaches its maximum value F_I and the snap-through activates; (II) self-equilibrated load-free configuration, where the equilibrium takes place in absence of external load even though the stresses in the bars are non-zero; (III) second critical point, where the load reaches the value $F_{III} = F_I$ and the equilibrium is again stable; (IV) specular undeformed configuration.

The characteristic configurations listed above allow to distinguish four regions: (a) compressive loading region; (b) snap-through region where the equilibrium is unstable; (c) unloading region where the bars are compressed; (d) tension region where the bars are subjected to tension.

2.3. Material models

2.3.1. Mooney-Rivlin (MR) material

In this work, the constitutive behavior of the rubber specimen is described by the compressible MR law, which is characterized by the stored energy function (Ciarlet & Geymonat, 1982)

$$W(\iota_1, \iota_2, \iota_3) = a(\iota_1 - 3) + b(\iota_2 - 3) + c(\iota_3 - 1) - (a + 2b + c) \log(\iota_3), \quad (13)$$

Figure 2: Characteristic configurations and regions.

where a , b and c are positive constants. The derivatives of the stored energy function (13) with respect to the invariants are computed and, by substitution into Eq. (9), the equilibrium equation in case of compressible MR material becomes

$$\bar{F} - 4\lambda_z \frac{H - \hat{w}}{\sqrt{B^2 + (H - \hat{w})^2}} Q = 0, \quad (14)$$

where

$$Q = (\bar{b}^2 - \bar{c} + P) \frac{1 + 2\bar{b}\lambda_z^2 + \lambda_z^4(\bar{c} - P)}{[\bar{b} + \lambda_z^2(\bar{c} - P)]^2}, \quad (15)$$

$$P = \frac{4(1 + 2\bar{b} + \bar{c})(\bar{b} + \bar{c}\lambda_z^2)^2}{\lambda_z^2} \left[1 + \bar{b}\lambda_z^2 - \sqrt{4(1 + 2\bar{b} + \bar{c})(\bar{b} + \bar{c}\lambda_z^2) + (1 + \bar{b}\lambda_z^2)^2} \right]^{-2},$$

and $\bar{F} = F/(tha)$, $\bar{b} = b/a$, $\bar{c} = c/a$.

2.3.2. Linear elastic (LE) material

The equilibrium problem of truss structures is often analyzed by considering only geometric nonlinearities (Kwasniewski, 2009; Ligaro & Valvo, 2006). This approach is outlined in the present section with the purpose of providing a comparison with the fully nonlinear formulation described previously, where a MR material is adopted.

In the model proposed by Kwasniewski (2009) and Ligaro & Valvo (2006) the material is assumed to behave according to a linearly elastic constitutive law characterized by the following stored energy function:

$$W(\epsilon_z) = \frac{1}{2} E \epsilon_z^2, \quad (16)$$

where E denotes the Young's modulus and $\epsilon_z = (l_m^2 - L_m^2) / (2L_m^2)$ is the axial component of strain given by the Green-Lagrange strain measure. The axial stress resultant acting on the rod is computed as

$$N_{LE} = th \frac{\partial W}{\partial \epsilon_z} = thE \frac{l_m^2 - L_m^2}{2L_m^2}. \quad (17)$$

The equilibrium equation of the von Mises truss in case of linear elastic material is derived by substituting Eq. (17) into Eq. (6), obtaining

$$F + 2thE \frac{l_m^2 - L_m^2}{2L_m^2} \sin \theta = 0. \quad (18)$$

Figure 3: Experimental device: (a) Photo of the top view (XZ plane); (b) Device components.

Recalling Eqs. (1) and (2), the kinematic relations (3) and the definition of the longitudinal stretch (5), the equilibrium takes the form

$$F - thE(\lambda_z^2 - 1) \frac{H - \hat{w}}{\sqrt{B^2 + (H - \hat{w})^2}} = 0. \quad (19)$$

3. Experimental investigation

3.1. Uniaxial tests for rubber characterization

The material used is a synthetic neoprene rubber with hardness value of 70 ± 5 ShA produced by FIP through polymerization of chloroprene (<https://www.fipitaly.it/en/products/catalogues/our-catalogues/neoprene-sheets-cr>). The rubber characterization is performed by carrying out separately uniaxial compression and tension tests. The testing machine is the Instron 5567, equipped with a 30 kN load cell for the compression test and a 1 kN load cell for the tension test.

Three squat cylindrical specimens of 28.85 mm diameter and 10.56 mm thickness are tested under compression. Three dog-bone specimens of 83.43 mm^2 cross section area and 65.25 mm effective length are tested under tension. The displacement rate is 0.5 and 50 mm/min for compression and tensile tests, respectively.

Nominal stress and stretch are computed for each test. The nominal stress vs. stretch curves in compression and tension are merged and the three resulting experimental curves are named S_1 , S_2 and S_3 . These experimental results are used in Section 6.1 to estimate the best fitting parameters of the MR constitutive law.

3.2. Experimental device for the von Mises truss

The experimental device of Figure 3a is designed specifically to simulate the von Mises truss subjected to a vertical load. The device is composed of three steel guides fixed on a supporting table. Control point C is forced to slide along the vertical guide, allowing only the vertical degree of freedom \hat{w} . Nodes C_1 and C_2 are placed on the horizontal guides and their distance can be adjusted according to the geometry of the problem (Figure 3b).

The hinges of the truss are realized with steel blocks that rotate around the corresponding nodes. The hinge in node C is connected to the hinges in C_1 and C_2 using two steel rods that avoid relative rotations. Namely, the terminal faces of the steel blocks are forced to remain parallel to one another. As shown in Figure 3a, the steel rods slide through hollow cylindrical guides. This allows the axial deformation of the

Table 1: Geometry of the von Mises truss and rubber specimens

Parameter	Value	Unit
θ_0	20	deg
L	146.5	mm
L_m	90	mm
L_r	28.25	mm
t	10	mm
h	20.5	mm

prismatic rubber specimen, which is glued to the hinge blocks with an adhesion primer for steel-rubber connection.

The theoretical formulation of the equilibrium presented in Section 2 does not include Eulerian buckling of the specimens. In order to adhere as much as possible with this, two hollow cylinders made of nylon are inserted in the steel rods. The function of the cylinders is to confine the rubber specimen so as to limit its bending deformation and prevent buckling. Note that, in Section 6.3, additional experimental tests will be carried out without confinement cylinders. This will allow to observe Eulerian buckling and investigate its effect on the equilibrium of the von Mises truss.

The contact between cylinder and rubber specimen affects the deformation of the rubber. For this reason the cylinders are carved in a way to ensure only three contact points with the specimen. A free space of 0.2 mm between cylinder and specimen is left in order to minimize the influence on the lateral deformation of the rubber.

The concentrated load F is applied through two synthetic fishing lines with a load capacity of 200 N. One end of both the lines is tied to the central hinge C , while the other ends are connected to containers where the load is manually placed. Two pulleys are placed on the two opposite sides of the vertical guide, between hinge C and the load containers. Each line slides through the corresponding pulley. In this way, the vertical load can be applied in both upward and downward directions.

Three pairs of specimens are tested. All the specimens have the same geometry, which is given in Table 1. The test consists in the application of a load that is gradually increased by adding weight in the container. For each load increment, the vertical displacement of node C is monitored by means of digital image correlation (DIC).

The test starts from the initial configuration (0). The load is applied downwards and the compression of the specimens increases as the load increases, until critical point (I) is reached and snap-through activates downwards. At this point the system is unloaded and the truss attains the specular undeformed configuration (IV). The load is then applied downwards and both specimens are subjected to tension. No unstable phenomena take place. The system is again unloaded and the truss comes back to configuration (IV). The load is now applied upwards and both specimens are subjected to compression until the truss attains critical point (III), where snap-through takes place in the upward direction. The entire equilibrium paths are finally obtained by repeating this procedure for each pair of specimens.

3.3. Digital image correlation (DIC) monitoring

The displacement field during the experimental test is acquired by means of DIC technology. The instrumentation used is Dantec Dynamics Q400. The DIC monitoring is performed in stereo mode (Grediac, 2004) by placing two cameras above the truss (Figure 4a). The displacement field is thus captured on the XZ plane at $Y = -t/2$. The optical device calibration and pre-processing operations are such to ensure a resolution of $\pm 20 \mu\text{m}$.

The upper surfaces of the rubber specimens, the hinge blocks and a portion of the vertical guide are painted with a random pattern for the DIC monitoring. Two masks are then defined for the displacement field monitoring. The investigated masks are shown in Figure 4b with framed white dashed areas. One mask is set on the vertical guide to acquire the displacement of control point C . The other mask traces the

Figure 4: (a) Set up of the DIC instrumentation and (b) view of the DIC cameras with the masks (white dashed frames) monitored during the experimental test.

margins of the left rubber specimen and it is used to obtain the displacement field of the specimen itself. Note that, given the symmetry of the problem, only the displacement field of the left rubber specimen is monitored.

The DIC cameras acquire a single frame for each load increment. The data resulting from the DIC monitoring of the experimental tests are discussed in Section 6.2.

4. Finite element analysis

The FE models are realized by using the FE code COMSOL Multiphysics[®] v.5.5 (Comsol, 2005). Four different FE models are created: two for the rubber characterization, one for compression and one for tension; two for the von Mises truss, which differ only in an internal solid constrain. A detailed description of each model is given in the following.

4.1. Models for rubber characterization

The FE constitutive curve is obtained by reproducing compression and tension tests on cylindrical and dog-bone specimens respectively. The rubber specimens are modeled in agreement with the samples geometries described in Section 3.2.

For the tension test, only the effective length of the dog-bone is modeled. Due to symmetry conditions, only one fourth of the specimen is modeled, as shown in Figure 5. The displacement component normal to each plane of symmetry is neglected.

The material is defined by setting the MR stored energy function (13) in the user defined material. Tetrahedral elements are used for compression while hexagonal elements for tension. In both cases, quadratic serendipity shape functions are employed.

A nonlinear incremental analysis is performed by applying a displacement in the z direction at the final cross section of the solid, as shown in Figure 5. The incremental steps are -0.005 and 0.5 mm for compression and tension respectively. The inertial load is not taken into account.

Figure 5: FE models for rubber characterization: Prismatic specimen under tension and cylindrical specimen under compression.

Figure 6: Details of the FE models: mesh, centers of rotation (CoR) and deformed configurations with contour plot of stretch λ_z . The deformed configuration at point (II) shows that Eulerian buckling takes place in model 2 but not in model 1.

4.2. Models for the von Mises truss

Two FE models are built for the simulation of the von Mises truss. The first model, named model 1, does not include Eulerian buckling of the rubber specimen. This model simulates the condition of the experimental test performed in this work, where the confinement cylinders prevent buckling phenomena. The second model, named model 2, simulates the response of the system without confinement cylinders. In this circumstance buckling plays an important role, which is discussed in detail in Section 6.3. Model 1 differs from model 2 only for an added constraint in order to avoid Eulerian buckling.

In both FE models, the MR material is defined in the same way of the previous section. The specimen geometries are set according to Table 1. Hexagonal elements with quadratic serendipity shape functions are used for the mesh.

Two symmetry conditions are employed. Firstly, only one bar is modeled because of the symmetry with respect to the vertical axis through the central node C . Secondly, only half of the bar is modeled thanks to the symmetry with respect to the XZ plane at $Y = 0$.

The hinge blocks are accounted for by using the feature rigid connector of the FE code. The rigid connector is a COMSOL constraining tool which attributes to a surface domain the rigid constraint associated to a moving or fixed center of rotation. The offset of the center of rotation with respect to the centroid of the surface element is L_r , which is the size of the hinge block. The final cross sections of the rubber specimen are constrained through two rigid connectors that are associated to the points C_1 and C of Figure 6.

A lower rigid connector is applied to the lower final cross section of the rubber specimen and associated to the fixed center of rotation C_1 . Likewise, an upper rigid connector is attributed to the final cross section of the rubber specimen and associated to the moving center of rotation C .

A nonlinear incremental analysis is performed by applying a vertical displacement \hat{w} at the upper center of rotation C . The incremental displacement step is -0.1 mm, ranging in the interval $\hat{w} \in [0, -3H]$. In addition, both rigid connectors are constrained to rotate of the rigid rotation $\psi(\hat{w})$ around the corresponding center of rotation. This constraint ensures that the final cross sections of the specimen remain coaxial during the deformation.

As previously pointed out, model 1 contains an additional constraint to the ones described above. Specifically, also the middle cross section of the specimen is constrained to rotate by $\psi(\hat{w})$ around the lower center of rotation C_1 . This kinematic constraint of model 1 ensures the absence of Eulerian buckling in the solution. In fact, the deformed configurations of Figure 6 show that at the characteristic point (II) only model 2 is affected by buckling.

5. Fitting of the rubber constitutive model

Stress and stretch data obtained from the uniaxial tests are used to perform a nonlinear fitting of the MR constitutive parameters a , b and c .

The parameters are collected into the parameter vector $\mathbf{p} = [a, b, c]^T$. The fitting function $s(\lambda_z, \mathbf{p})$ is the nominal stress vs. stretch relation for a compressible MR material, which is obtained by writing Eq. (8) in case of MR material ($s = N/th$). The objective function $\text{obj}(\mathbf{p})$ is defined as the averaged sum of normalized square error between simulated and experimental data, namely

$$\text{obj}(\mathbf{p}) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^n [s(\lambda_{zi}, \mathbf{p}) - s_i]^2}{\sum_i^n s(\lambda_{zi}, \mathbf{p})^2}}, \quad (20)$$

where n is the number of data points, s_i and λ_{zi} are experimental nominal stress and stretch respectively, while $s(\lambda_{zi}, \mathbf{p})$ is the fitting function sampled at the data points.

The minimization of the objective function (20) is performed via a genetic algorithm (Whitley, 1994). Specifically, the fitting procedure is implemented in a MATLAB[®] code by using the *ga* function of the *global optimization toolbox*.

At first, an unconstrained optimization was carried out. The optimal value of parameter c provided by the algorithm was six orders of magnitude larger than parameters a and b ($\bar{c} \approx 10^6$). Although the stress vs. stretch curve was accurately depicted, this result was treated with suspicion. In fact, an application to the nonlinear bending theory reported in (Falope et al., 2019) led to unsatisfying results. Therefore, a constrained optimization was later carried out. The following lower and upper bounds of parameters were set:

$$a \in [10^2, 10^4], \quad b \in [10^2, 10^4], \quad c \in [10^3, 2 \times 10^5],$$

where the values are expressed in kPa.

6. Results and discussion

6.1. Rubber characterization

The stress vs. stretch curves S_1 , S_2 and S_3 resulting from the experimental uniaxial tests are shown in Figure 7. The constrained optimization is carried out for each of these three set of data. The best fitting parameters obtained are listed in Table 2.

The values of the objective function are around 5–6%, which indicate that the result of the optimization is accurate. This is confirmed by the corresponding values of coefficient of determination R^2 , that are near 0.94. This is a satisfactory result when dealing with large deformations. Table 2 shows mean value and standard deviation of each parameter over the three simulations. The standard deviation of parameter c is

Figure 7: Uniaxial nominal stress vs. stretch curves provided by experimental tests on three rubber specimens S_1 , S_2 and S_3 , analytic formulation (MR and LE materials) and FE model. Analytic and FE constitutive behaviors are obtained with the mean values of the best fitting constitutive parameters given in Table 2.

Table 2: Best fitting parameters of the Mooney-Rivlin material

Const. param.	Experimental curve			Mean \pm Dev.St
	S_1	S_2	S_3	
a (kPa)	442	461	468	457 ± 13
b (kPa)	391	366	386	381 ± 13
c (kPa)	35092	30211	29971	31758 ± 2889
obj(\mathbf{p}) (%)	6.614	5.866	5.938	-
R^2	0.934	0.941	0.940	-

Figure 8: Experimental, analytic (MR and LE materials) and FE equilibrium paths with reference steps and characteristic configurations and regions.

not very low, but its variations do not influence much the constitutive response, therefore this result is still considered reliable. The mean values of constitutive parameters a , b and c are thus chosen as optimal set of parameters.

The optimal set of parameters is introduced into the fitting function and into the FE model. The resulting analytic and FE stress vs. stretch curves are shown in Figure 7, along with the experimental one.

Analytic MR and FE curves are both derived with homogeneous deformations and MR constitutive law, thus they perfectly overlap. Good agreement is also found with the experimental data in compression, while in tension the MR constitutive law is not very accurate when deformations are large. However, the stretch of the rubber specimen during the experimental test on the von Mises truss ranges in the gray area of Figure 7. Within this range, both compression and tension are satisfactorily depicted by both analytic MR and FE curves.

Although in the range of interest the result is accurate enough, some considerations must be made. The detail of Figure 7 shows that, for relatively small contractions of the bars, the experimental constitutive behavior is stiffer than the analytic MR one. On the contrary, small extensions are well described by the analytic MR constitutive law. However, while the extension increases, the accuracy of the analytic MR law with respect to the experimental data decreases. In particular, the experimental curve is less stiff.

Figure 7 shows also the analytic LE constitutive law. It is obvious that, for large deformations, this material model is completely wrong compared to the real behavior of the rubber specimen. One may think that in the range of interest (gray area) this model assumption provides a good approximation. However, nonlinearity of rubber appears for rather small deformations and, as shown in the detail of Figure 7, the analytic LE law is not accurate even if the uniaxial deformation is not very large.

6.2. von Mises truss

The equilibrium paths derived from experimental tests, analytic model (MR and LE materials) and FE simulation are shown in Figure 8. Displacement \hat{w} is normalized with respect to the height H of the truss and load F is normalized with respect to the Eulerian buckling load of the system in undeformed configuration, expressed as

$$F_{\text{bk}} = \frac{8\pi^2 EI_x}{L_m^2} \sin(\theta_0), \quad (21)$$

where I_x is the cross section's moment of inertia with respect to axis x and E is the Young's modulus of the rubber, which is computed from the MR constitutive parameters as (Falope et al., 2019)

$$E = \frac{4(a+b)(a+4b+3c)}{a+3b+2c}. \quad (22)$$

Table 3: Normalized vertical displacement $\bar{w} = \hat{w}/H$ and relative error $e_r = |1 - \bar{w}/\bar{w}_{\text{MR}}|$.

Step	Analytic			FEM				Experimental			
	MR	LE		Model 1		S_1		S_2		S_3	
	\bar{w}_{MR}	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$
1	0.30	/	/	0.28	6.67	0.29	2.47	0.28	6.76	0.26	11.99
2	1.70	/	/	1.72	1.18	1.78	4.47	1.74	2.22	1.74	2.5
3	2.11	2.11	0.24	2.11	0.24	2.11	0.04	2.10	0.73	2.11	0.14
4	2.27	2.25	0.88	2.26	0.44	2.3	1.15	2.28	0.37	2.30	1.06
Char.pts.	\bar{w}_{MR}	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$	\bar{w}	$e_r(\%)$
(I)	0.46	0.43	5.49	0.46	0	0.42	8.79	0.48	5.27	0.44	3.30
(III)	1.54	1.57	1.62	1.54	0	1.56	1.13	1.52	1.55	1.56	1.05

The error of the analytic LE solution can not be computed at steps 1 and 2 because the LE equilibrium path does not reach the experimental load applied.

Note that the rubber specimens are considered clamped to the hinge blocks. Accordingly, Eq. (21) is derived introducing the buckling load of a double-clamped beam $N_{\text{bk}} = 4\pi^2 EI_x/L_m^2$ into Eq. (6).

Overall, there is a good agreement between experimental results, analytic path with MR material and FE path. The three main reasons of discrepancy between these results are discussed in the following. Considerations on the equilibrium path with the assumption of LE material will be given at the end of this section.

Firstly, the equilibrium equation (14) is based on the hypothesis of homogeneous deformation. However, for both FE model and experimental test this is not true. In both cases the final cross sections of the specimen are clamped to the rigid hinge blocks. This influences the deformation of the areas near the hinges.

Secondly, as shown in Figure 7, the experimental constitutive behavior is stiffer than the analytic one for relatively small contractions of the bars. This explains why for both regions (a) and (c) of Figure 8 the experimental data show higher stiffness. On the contrary, small extensions are well described by the analytic constitutive law. Indeed, the analytic curve fits well the experimental data in region (d). However, as the extension increases, the discrepancy between experimental, analytic and FE results increases as well. This because the accuracy of the analytic constitutive law decreases for large extensions.

Lastly, geometric imperfections and friction in the guides of the experimental device play a role on accuracy of the data. Although friction is reduced by using lubricant, its contribute is not negligible for low values of load. In fact, it contributes to increase the stiffness of the experimental curve close to characteristic points (0) and (VI).

Four reference steps in terms of applied load are selected and reported in Figure 8. The values of normalized displacement $\bar{w} = \hat{w}/H$ of node C are given in Table 3, for each reference step and for critical points (I) and (III). Relative errors of FE simulation and experimental tests with respect to the analytic solution are also given.

The highest experimental errors are committed close to critical points (I) and (III) because it is hard to catch the exact configuration where snap-through takes place. Indeed, the reference load steps with highest errors are step 1 and step 2, due to their proximity to the critical points. Overall, the results are satisfactory and the errors are largely acceptable.

The solution derived with the assumption of LE material, expressed by Eq. (19), is also represented in Figure 8. As expected, for low values of \hat{w} this solution provides a good approximation of the behavior of the truss. However, as the magnitude of displacement increases, the discrepancy rises. The linear constitutive behavior is not able to capture the increasing and decreasing of stiffness of the rubber specimens when subjected, respectively, to finite uniaxial compressive and tensile deformations. This is the reason why in regions (a), (b) and (c), where the bars are compressed, the equilibrium path with LE material is less stiff

Figure 9: Relative error in terms of load committed along the equilibrium path by assuming a LE constitutive law.

than the one obtained with MR material. Same goes for region (d), where the bars are both stretched and thus the linear solution is stiffer than the one with MR material.

The sensible difference between experimental results and equilibrium path with LE material shows that, in general, this assumption is not appropriate. An accurate analysis of equilibrium and stability of truss structures requires a fully nonlinear model. It is worth saying that the geometry of the truss plays an important role in this matter. In fact, Figure 9 shows that the more the inclination is low, the more the deformations of the bars are small and a linear model might give satisfactory results. For an inclination $\theta_0 = 45^\circ$, the maximum error committed in terms of load is more than seven times the value of critical buckling load F_{bk} , which is obviously a result that can not be accepted. As the inclination decreases, the maximum error decreases as well. It is reasonable to say that, for inclinations lower than $\theta_0 = 10^\circ$, the approximation given by a linear elastic based model can be considered acceptable. In fact, for $\theta_0 = 15^\circ$ the maximum relative error is still rather large (around 15%), while for $\theta_0 = 10^\circ$ there is a drastic reduction, with a value less than 1%.

In conclusion, in a general case it is not true that the deformations are small enough to adopt a linear constitutive law. However, when the inclination of the truss is less than 10° this approximation might be accepted, depending on the accuracy required. Note that such result is valid for the rubber specimen analyzed in the present work. If the material behavior is different, for instance showing a stronger nonlinearity, this conclusion might be erroneous.

6.3. Further considerations and Eulerian buckling

The experimental device described in Section 3.2 is specifically designed to avoid Eulerian buckling of the rubber specimen. Figure 10 shows a contour plot of the transversal displacement component u_1 at load increment 8 and the line plots of $u_1(0, -t/2, z_1)$. It is clear that a slight bending deformation occurred during the tests, but it was contained by the nylon cylinders. In particular, the values of u_1 until load increment 4 are close to the DIC accuracy ($\pm 20 \mu\text{m}$), while from load increment 5 it is obvious that a sensible bending deformation started. This indicates that actual buckling phenomena took place presumably around load increment 5, for an applied load of 27.5 N.

After load increment 5, the transversal displacement profiles are much closer to each other. This reveals that the specimen is crushing against the cylinder and the confinement effect activates, limiting the bending deformation and ensuring a behavior as close as possible to a homogeneous deformation. The necessity of the confinement cylinders in the experimental tests is thus confirmed.

The experimental evidence of buckling is supported by the simulation provided by FE model 2, the outcome of which is shown in Figure 11. The load paths of model 1 and model 2 perfectly agree until the critical buckling load is reached at $\hat{w}_{bk,FE}$. At this point, model 2 experiences buckling and deviates from

Figure 10: Line plots and contour plot at load increment 8 of displacement component u_1 in the principal reference system $C_1x_1y_1z_1$ for the specimen S_3 .

Figure 11: Eulerian instability investigated from numerical (FE), analytic and experimental points of view: (a) Experimental test without confinement cylinders put in comparison with the equilibrium paths given by FE models and critical load curve computed with the theoretical approach proposed in the present work (Eq. (26), black curve); (b) The detail shows that the formulation proposed in this work provides the best agreement with experiments.

model 1. This would represent the behavior of the truss in the event that the confinement cylinders are removed.

From an analytic point of view, buckling occurs at the intersection between equilibrium path and Eulerian buckling load. Bazzucchi et al. (2017) investigated the interaction between snap-through and Eulerian instability, providing the following theoretical evaluation of the critical load for the von Mises truss:

$$f_{\text{bk},[3]}(\hat{w}) = \frac{8\pi^2 EI_x}{L_m^2} \sin\theta. \quad (23)$$

Note that Eq. (23) shows dependence on the constitutive parameters through E , expressed by Eq. (22), and on the geometry of the system through L_m and I_x .

The formulation given by Bazzucchi et al. (2017) does not take into account variations of the material constitutive behavior while the truss changes its configuration due to the applied load. Furthermore, geometric quantities L_m and I_x should be computed in deformed configuration. Hence, in the present work, an accurate prediction of the Eulerian instability is given by expressing such constitutive and geometric quantities in deformed configuration. Firstly, the Young's modulus is replaced by the tangent elastic modulus, function of the deformation, defined as derivative of the nominal axial stress $s = N/th$ (Eq. (8)) with respect

Figure 12: The DIC photo during the experimental test without confinement cylinders shows that, when critical buckling load of the rubber specimen is reached, Eulerian buckling takes place and the equilibrium loses its stability.

to stretch λ_z

$$E(\lambda_z) = \frac{\partial s}{\partial \lambda_z} = 2 [4\lambda_z \lambda \lambda' (\lambda^2 W_{,3} + \lambda W_{,2}) + \lambda^4 (\lambda_z W'_{,3} + W_{,3}) + 2\lambda^2 (\lambda_z W'_{,2} + W_{,2}) + \lambda_z W'_{,1} + W_{,1}], \quad (24)$$

where λ is the transversal stretch given by Eq. (7) and symbol ' indicates the derivative with respect to stretch λ_z . The expression of $E(\lambda_z)$ for a MR material is obtained by specializing Eq. (24) to the stored energy function of Eq. (13). As for the geometric quantities of Eq. (23), L_m is replaced by the deformed rubber length l_m (Eq. (2)), while moment of inertia I_x is computed as

$$I_x(\lambda_z) = \frac{1}{12} (\lambda h) (\lambda t)^3, \quad (25)$$

where again λ is the transversal stretch given in function of λ_z by Eq. (7). Finally, the Eulerian buckling load for a MR material computed in deformed configuration is expressed as

$$f_{\text{bk,MR}}(\hat{w}) = \frac{8\pi^2 E(\lambda_z) I_x(\lambda_z)}{l_m^2} \sin \theta, \quad (26)$$

in which $E(\lambda_z)$ and $I_x(\lambda_z)$ are given by Eqs. (24) and (25), respectively. The critical load curve of Eq. (26) is depicted in Figure 11 with black color.

To understand which formulation provides the best prediction of Eulerian instability, an experimental test without confinement cylinders is carried out. When the system attains the critical buckling load, Eulerian buckling takes place and the truss snaps before the snap-through load is reached. At this point the test ends and the last configuration monitored is the one right before Eulerian instability. Figure 12 shows a DIC photo of the specimen that, without the presence of the confinement cylinders, is free to undergo bending deformation.

The results of the experiment without confinement cylinders are given in Figure 11, in terms of applied load vs. vertical displacement \hat{w} . It is clearly visible that the prediction of Eulerian instability given by the formulation proposed in the present work (Eq. (26)) is very accurate. The result provided by FE model 2 also deserves some consideration. From Figure 11b one can notice that the critical buckling load of FE model 2 lies in the middle of the two analytical predictions given by Eqs. (26) and (23). The reason why FE model 2 is not very accurate is that the best fitting parameters of Table 2 are obtained by fitting the constitutive model to uniaxial compressive and tensile tests only. Hence, it is not guaranteed that such parameters provide accurate solutions also in case of bending of the specimens. In light of this, it is obvious that the simulation of FE model 2, which involves bending of the bars, can not be considered reliable.

Figure 13: Detail of the analytic predictions of Eulerian buckling and contributes of each kinematic and constitutive quantity: $f_{bk,[3]}$ is the critical load computed with the formulation of Bazzucchi et al. (2017), $f_{bk,MR}$ is expressed by Eq. (26), while $f_{bk,Lm}$, $f_{bk,Ix}$ and $f_{bk,E}$ are obtained considering one by one the contribution of functions l_m , $I_x(\lambda_z)$ and $E(\lambda_z)$ into Eq. (26).

However, it still gives an idea of the Eulerian buckling load and adds confidence in both experimental and analytical predictions.

Figure 13 shows a comparison of the analytic predictions of Eulerian buckling given by the formulation of this work and the one proposed by Bazzucchi et al. (2017). It is clearly visible that the best prediction is given by the formulation proposed in the present work (Eq. (26)). Instead, the critical load with the approach of Bazzucchi et al. (2017) provides a severe underestimation. This happens for two reasons. Firstly, Eq. (23) does not capture the fact that with the increasing of compression the response of the rubber specimen becomes more and more stiff. Instead, this is taken into account in Eq. (26) by introducing a tangent elastic modulus that is function of λ_z . Secondly, Eq. (23) does not consider the increase of moment of inertia I_x and the decrease of length L_m of the specimen. Both phenomena are introduced in the formulation of this work with quantities $I_x(\lambda_z)$ and l_m in Eq. (26).

The contributes to Eulerian instability of the kinematic and constitutive quantities appearing in Eq. (26) are graphically represented in Figure 13. Given that length L_m has exponent 2 in the computation of the critical load, one may expect that the most relevant contribution is the length variation. However, Figure 13 shows that $E(\lambda_z)$ plays the most important role. This demonstrates that, for an accurate prediction of Eulerian instability, it is necessary to carefully take into account the material nonlinearity. Note that the contribution of $I_x(\lambda_z)$ is more or less the same as the one given by the length variation. Therefore, this is also an important contribution to consider for a correct estimation.

7. Conclusions

The von Mises truss subjected to a vertical load is analyzed from theoretical, numerical and experimental points of view. The equilibrium is written in deformed configuration and specialized to the case of compressible MR constitutive law, which is assumed for the rubber material considered in this work. A LE constitutive behavior is also considered with the purpose of providing a comparison between the results. An experimental device that reproduces the von Mises truss subjected to a vertical load is presented and the tests are monitored with DIC technology. Two FE models are developed in order to give comparisons and discuss the effect of Eulerian buckling on the equilibrium paths.

The experimental results and the FE simulation of model 1 show good agreement with the analytical MR results. This provides a validation of the theoretical formulation. Although the assumption of homogeneous deformation does not perfectly depict the actual behavior of the rubber specimens, it is demonstrated that it is appropriate and accurate. Hence, the results demonstrate that the analytical model presented in this work gives an accurate description of equilibrium and post-critical behavior of truss structures. Furthermore, the comparison with the results obtained under the assumption of LE constitutive law show that the material

nonlinearity can not be neglected. This approximation is, in general, not accurate for the analysis of truss structures with large displacements.

The kinematics of the analytical model for the von Mises truss does not consider bending deformation due to Eulerian buckling. However, a simple formulation to predict Eulerian instability is derived by using the kinematic and constitutive relations furnished by the analytical model, which allow to consider both geometrical and material nonlinearities. Additional experiments are carried out removing the confinement cylinders and Eulerian buckling is experimentally observed. The comparison of the results show that the analytical approach presented in this work gives an accurate prediction of this phenomenon. The interaction between snap-through and Eulerian buckling will be further examined in forthcoming works, in which theoretical formulations in three-dimensional finite elasticity will be developed and new experimental tests will be carried out.

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